

DYNAMIC NOTATION – A SOLUTION TO THE CONUNDRUM OF NON-STANDARD MUSIC PRACTICE

Georg Hajdu

Center for Microtonal Music and Multimedia
Hamburg University of Music and Theater
georg.hajdu@hfmt-hamburg.de

ABSTRACT

This paper discusses *dynamic notation*—a method allowing, in a notation environment, instant switching between different staff views or *notation styles*, thus creating a common ground for practitioners of non-standard music, such as composers, performers, conductors and scholars. So far very few notation programs have explored this notion as much as it should have been. Therefore, we have implemented in the MaxScore Editor (a notation editor designed to run in Max or Ableton Live) a plugin structure for different notation styles based on a set of maps and queries executed during note entry and rendering—affecting music glyph choice and placement. We will give an in-depth analysis of the methods used for equidistant scales, non-octave tunings, music in just intonation as well as for instrument-specific layouts and will conclude with a description of a scenario in which dynamic notation was used for the transcription and performance of Alexander Scriabin’s piano poem *Vers la Flamme* op. 72 by an ensemble of acoustic Bohlen-Pierce instruments.

1. INTRODUCTION

In his 2001 book *The Language of New Media* [1] media theorist Lev Manovich points out that *new media objects* need to fulfill certain criteria among which *variability* is related to *dynamic* delivery of content. New media objects can exist in multiple versions such as, in case of an audio recording, a high-definition 192kHz 64-bit file, a standard CD-quality file, a lossless ALAC or a lossy compressed mp3 file.

Variability is key to solving the conundrum practitioners of non-standard music are facing when performing such music. The prerequisite is that the music is created and/or delivered by a computer-based system capable of

switching between different views or representations in real time¹.

Rudimentary dynamic notation is common amongst notation environments. Most typically, a program will let the users switch between regular and percussion notation, or piano roll view. Bach [3], PWGL [4], OpenMusic [5] and InScore [6] as well as the lesser known Siren [7] and CMN [8] represent music in various measured and non-measured ways but lack a simple plugin structure for adding new views dynamically, hence requiring a higher degree of meddling with the code to achieve results comparable to the MaxScore Editor.

2. NON-STANDARD MUSIC PRACTICE

The practice of music in non-standard tunings has been hampered by, besides the lack of appropriate instruments, a “confusion of tongues” in respect to how this kind of music is supposed to be notated. Notation should cater to the needs of the people involved: A player performs best if the notation is close to the layout of the instrument played. For that matter, guitarists have been using tablature for centuries and Harry Partch’s notations for pitched percussion, for instance, are most often concerned with the topology of the instrument rather than actual pitch [9]. The notations for the Bohlen-Pierce clarinets which exist in two sizes (soprano and tenor) as well as the modified Bohlen-Pierce alto recorder also use fingering notation, taking advantage of the learned correspondence between finger position and sounding pitch on a traditional instrument. We can thus call this approach *instrumental notation*.

A composer or arranger works best when using a notation that represents the logic of a particular tuning. Sabat and von Schweinitz, for instance, have developed an elegant solution of representing frequency ratios in *just intonation* by designing a large set of accidentals [10]. Equidistant tunings in turn benefit from representing equal pitch distances as such. The diatonic Guidonian notation already poses difficulties when it comes to coherently representing whole-tone or atonal/12-tone music,

Copyright: © 2015 Georg Hajdu. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License 3.0 Unported, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

¹ We need to point out that our use of the term *view* differs from Dannenberg [2] who refers to “a data-structure that corresponds to a presentation.”

but fails bitterly at non-octave tunings such as the Bohlen-Pierce scale. Equidistant notations, such as the Hauer-Steffens notation [11] have the advantage that transpositions and transformations of tone gestalts become evident, but have been rejected in history because of cultural and economic implications, and most likely also because of the cognitive mismatch between notation and the piano layout with its black and white keys. There is no reason, though, to shy away from introducing equidistant notation for tunings other than 12EDO (and its related, circle-of-fifths-based tunings). We dub this approach *logical notation*.

A conductor, finally, has different concerns as he/she needs to grasp the meaning of the different notation styles used in rehearsals and performances. A conductor needs to hear, identify and compare the sounding events to the score and to an internalized template—a feat facilitated by years of intensive training and practice. He/she may be best served by the representation of music in traditional Guidonian notation, enriched by an extended set of accidentals or indications of deviations written above the notes. This may also be the notation of choice for instruments such as standard string or wind instruments. We will name this approach *conventional* or *cognitive* notation as it depends on internalized templates.

As we are attempting to establish a taxonomy for notational approaches, we also need to concede that these distinctions are arbitrary to a certain extent. *Instrumental* and *conventional* notations have a common root originating from the *logic* of the music in practice when its notation was standardized.

2.1 Scenarios

One can conceive of the following scenarios in which dynamic notation may be welcome:

All musicians are reading from computer/tablet screens of either isolated devices or machines in a networked arrangement. Alternatively, only the person guiding the rehearsals/performance uses an electronic device while the other members of the ensemble read from paper-based print-outs. In the latter case, the responsibility lies in him/her to guide the communication on notational aspects. Finally, both scores and parts are paper-based, but they contain, on different staves, alternative representations of the music to be performed. Even in this case, a

system capable of changing views in real-time can vastly simplify the process of creating scores and parts.

3. IMPLEMENTATION

A plugin structure for dynamic switching between notation styles has been implemented for the MaxScore Editor. MaxScore is a Max Java object designed and maintained by Nick Didkovsky since 2007 to bring music notation to the Max environment [12].

Since 2010 the author is developing an editor, which also interfaces with Ableton Live via Max for Live. As opposed to the Bach notation objects, which—being native Max externals—provide better integration in the Max environment, the MaxScore Editor is based on a hybrid approach consisting of the core mxj object and a periphery made of numerous C and Java externals, Max abstractions and JavaScript objects (forming the editor’s GUI, among other functions; see **Figure 1**). The advantage of a hybrid system is its high degree of adaptability and versatility. As the communication between the core and the periphery is based on messages, they can easily be intercepted and reinterpreted according to current demand.

The editor handles notation styles like plugins and loads them as Max patches dynamically from a folder in MaxScore package hierarchy. It is thus very straightforward to add new styles to the existing repertoire.

Every notation style defines 5 attributes:

- A name of the notation style appearing in the style menu of the Staff Manager.
- The name of the Max patch containing pitch maps,
- The number of staff lines employed by the style.
- The micromap to be used for the rendering of accidentals.
- The name of the clef appearing on the staff.
- If a non-standard clef is being specified such as Bohlen-Pierce T-clef, an additional definition needs to be given in the form of clef name, glyph, x and y offsets as well as font name and size.

Figure 1. The nested structure of the MaxScore Editor plugin system.

3.1 Micromaps

Micromaps were introduced in 2011 to allow higher resolution representations of divisions of the semitone. While MaxScore’s pitch attribute is stored, processed and played back in 32-bit floating-point precision, the drawing messages generated by the object are limited to quarter tones. Hence, MaxScore would fail to accurately represent music in eighth tones (the standard among spectral composers) or twelfth tones (used by composers such as Ivan Wyschnegradsky and Ezra Sims). Micromaps are Max abstractions that intercept drawing messages and query the pitch and accidental preferences attribute of the corresponding note. Based on this information and the notation style chosen by the user, a micromap sends new, more fine-grained drawing messages to the MaxScore canvas. Currently, the maximum precision is sixteenth tones in Sagittal notation, taking advantage of the enormous set of accidentals in the Bravura font, just recently released by Steinberg [13].

Figure 2. 16th-tone notation with the Sagittal font.

How is this mapping performed? This is best explained by an example: After entering a middle c a sixteenth note sharp (pitch = 60.125) the MaxScore object sends out a drawing message with 9 items (accidental, x, y, zoom, parent object, measure, staff, track and note indexes) such as:

```
“no_accidental 75.555557 81. 0.5 Note 0. 0. 0. 0.”2
```

The five last items are sliced off and a “getNoteInfo 0. 0. 0. 0.” query is sent to the core object. It returns a string in XML format which is being parsed and sent back to the micromap. Of the many note attributes, *pitch* and *accidental* information is being retained to calculate the pitch zone a particular accidental is applied to.

The zone index Z is given by this formula ($rnpc$ = floating point remainder of natural pitch class, n = division of the semitone, $sgn = -1$ for ACCPREF = flat and $sgn = 1$ for ACCPREF = sharp):

$$Z = [sgn \ rnpc \ n + \frac{1}{n+2}] \quad (1)$$

In our case, the result would be

$$[1 \cdot 0.125 \cdot 8 + 0.0625] = 1$$

This value is fed into a zone-to-glyph-name lookup table (a Max coll object), which sends out `accSagittal5CommaUp`, the name of the Sagittal accidental in the Standard Music Font Layout specification on which the Bravura font is based [13].

This message is combined with the rest of the message into

```
“accSagittal5CommaUp 75.555557 81. 0.5 Note 0. 0. 0. 0.”
```

of which the first four items are further processed:

The zoom value scales the font size as well as x and y offsets. The accidental name is sent to another instance of a Max coll object which returns

```
“4 -4 0 Bravura 24” (glyph, x offset, y offset, font name, font size).
```

² no_accidental messages will be ignored by the drawing engine, but are a prerequisite for mapping.

This information is then translated into three separate Max lcd messages:

1. “font Bravura 24.”
2. “moveto 71.555557 82.” (due to various reasons a y offset of 1 is applied to all glyphs)
3. “write 1”

3.2 Notation Styles

For the representation of music in the Extended Helmholtz-Ellis JI Pitch Notation created by Sabat and von Schweinitz we had to go a step further. A problem arises when the MaxScore object is no longer capable of representing the correct *mpc* in case of complex harmonic relationships such as $75/49$ ($3^1 \cdot 5^2 \cdot 7^{-2}$). According to the logic of the Helmholtz-Ellis notation the interval size of 736.9 cents—when applied to a middle *c*—would have to be represented by an *f* with two accidentals, a double-sharp with two arrows down and a raise by two septimal commas (see **Figure 4**) The diatonic pitch class is calculated by moving along the circle of fifths, which in our case would be moving 13 ticks in clock-wise direction, thus amounting to an *f* double-sharp. This conflicts with the pitch class natively assigned by MaxScore which is g^3 . The solution was found by creating a specific Just Intonation *notation style*. Kuuskankare and Laurson [14] use a similar term (*notational style*) denoting changes in notation that include not only pitch but other aspects such as measured/non-measured notation.

A notation style is basically defined by two maps (map and inverse map) but also requires the definition of an additional attribute. This can be easily achieved in MaxScore where an unlimited number of dimensions can be added to notes and intervals first by applying the “setInstrumentDimension” message to a particular staff and then setting note dimensions values individually. Considering this, we have defined an additional *originalPitch* dimension which holds the pitch of a note regardless of how it is represented graphically in the score and is also used for playback.

After choosing a notation style from a menu in the Staff Manager, all notes for a given staff are passed to the inverse map of the abstraction of the *current* notation style (*default* for new scores) to restore the *originalPitch* attribute. Then all events are routed to the map of the abstraction of the *selected* notation style⁴. Here the *pitch* attribute is set to the position of the note it is supposed to occupy in the given notation style.

³ MaxScore stops considering enharmonic spellings for ranges outside of double flats and sharps (maximum considered deviation = 225 cents; in case of $75/49$ the deviation is 236.9 cents).

⁴ NB.: Instead of current and selected, we could also use the terms old and new.

Figure 3. The style menu in the MaxScore Editor Staff Manager. The equal divisions of the semitone on top don’t require additional pitch mapping and are part of the *default* notation style.

Data flow in and out a plugin is controlled by a JavaScript object—one instance per staff. The object also receives messages when a note is being created, in which case, *originalPitch* is calculated by sending its *pitch* through the *inverse map*. For instance, when a note is created in T clef below the bottom staff line (pitch = 59), *originalPitch* will be immediately set to 49.98. Likewise, the *pitch* attribute will automatically be updated after a transposition, which, conveniently, can be done across different notation styles. While a *map*, generally, only receives *originalPitch* values from the JavaScript object, an *inverse map* receives a list of 9 current note, staff and measure attributes. The *inverse map* subsequently filters useful attributes, hence the dollar sign arguments in the notation style Max patches.

3.3 Examples

We will now more closely examine some of the notation styles implemented in the Max Score Editor.

3.3.1 Just Intonation

Definition: ““Just Intonation” justintonation 5 mM-JI default”

Figure 4. The Bohlen-Pierce scale in Extended Helmholtz-Ellis JI Pitch notation

As pointed out above, certain ratios lead to a situation where the actual pitch is more than 225 cents off its natural “anchor” tone. Having introduced *originalPitch* as an attribute for correct playback, the *pitch* attribute can now be “arbitrarily” moved to a tone above or below—thus displaying the correct pitch/accidental combination. The calculations involved are fairly complex and have been described in [12].

longer rely on a common notational reference internalized by years of training such as with the 12-tone system. Applying various styles in an arrangement for Bohlen-Pierce instruments proved to be a viable approach for editing, printing and rehearsing. More notation styles will be added as we further develop this version of the software, which currently is in a beta state and can be downloaded from <http://www.computermusicnotation.com>.

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank the *Behörde für Forschung und Wissenschaft Hamburg* for supporting our research in the framework of its *Landesforschungsförderung*. I would also like to thank Benedict Carey and Todd Harrop for proof reading.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] L. Manovich, *The Language of New Media*. MIT Press, 2001.
- [2] R. Dannenberg, "A structure for representing, displaying and editing music", *Proceedings of International Computer Music Conference*, 1986, pp. 153–160.
- [3] A. Agostini and D. Ghisi, "Real-time computer-aided composition with bach", *Contemporary Music Review*, vol. 32, no. 1, 2013, pp. 41-48.
- [4] M. Laurson, M. Kuuskankare, and V. Norilo, "An Overview of PWGL, a Visual Programming Environment for Music," *Computer Music Journal*, vol. 33, no. 1, 2009.
- [5] G. Assayag and C. Agon, "OpenMusic Architecture," *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*, 1996.
- [6] <http://inscore.sourceforge.net>.
- [7] <http://fastlabinc.com/Siren/>.
- [8] <https://ccrma.stanford.edu/software/cmn/cmn/cmn.html>.
- [9] H. Partch, *Genesis of a Music: Monophony*, University of Wisconsin Press, 1949.
- [10] <http://www.marcsabat.com/pdfs/notation.pdf>.
- [11] G. Read, *Music Notation: A Manual of Modern Practice*. Crescendo Book, 1979, p. 32.
- [12] G. Hajdu and N. Didkovsky, "MaxScore – Current State of the Art," *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*, 2012.
- [13] <http://www.smuf1.org>.
- [14] M. Kuuskankare and M. Laurson, "Expressive Notation Package - an Overview," *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Music Information Retrieval*, 2004.
- [15] J. Yasser, *Theory of Evolving Tonality*, American Library of Musicology, 1932.
- [16] N.-L. Müller, K. Orlandatou and G. Hajdu, "Starting Over – Chances Afforded by a New Scale," in: *1001 Microtones*, M. Stahnke and S. Safari (Eds.). Von Bockel, 2014, pp. 127–172.
- [17] H. Bohlen, "13 Tonstufen in der Duodezime," *Acustica*, vol. 39, no. 2, pp. 76–86, 1978.
- [18] M.V. Mathews, J. R. Pierce, A. Reeves and L. A. Roberts, "Theoretical and experimental explorations of the Bohlen–Pierce scale," *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 84, p. 1214, 1988.
- [19] P. Loui, *Acquiring a New Musical System*. PhD thesis, 2007. http://cnmat.berkeley.edu/library/acquiring_new_musical_system.
- [20] <http://www.sfoxclarinets.com>.
- [21] <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mbira>
- [22] http://japanese.imslp.info/files/imglnks/usimg/5/52/IMSLP12740-Scriabin_-_Op.72.pdf
- [23] S. Sayegh, "Fingering for String Instruments with the Optimum Path Paradigm", *Computer Music Journal*, vol. 13, no. 6, p. 7684, 1989.
- [24] D. R. Tuohy and W. D. Potter, "Generating Guitar Tablature with LHF Notation Via DGA and ANN," *Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Industrial and Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence and Expert Systems, IEA/AIE*, pp. 244-253, 2006.
- [25] http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Studie_II
- [26] Sara Adhitya, Mika Kuuskankare, "Connecting SUM with computer-assisted composition in PWGL: Recreating the graphic scores of Anestis Logothetis," *Proceedings of the Joint ICMC/SMC Conference*, Athens, 2014.

Webpages all accessed on January 28, 2015.